

ROLE OF INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Turayeva Nazira Ibragimovna

A teacher and a master of The Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Abstract:

This article is about interactive learning, which is a modern method of learning that includes all participants in the educational process, including teachers and students. This teaching style is now extensively employed everywhere: in schools, universities, courses, and trainings, because it is incredibly effective not only in terms of learning knowledge, but also in terms of developing personal skills and character development in students. It is critical that interactive teaching methods be used in practically all types of training: individual meetings, group meetings, online training, and telephone training. The article also looked on students' participation in interactive activities in English classes. Learning a foreign language in an engaging manner can provide incredible results. Interactive ways of teaching English, in particular, are far more effective than traditional lessons. During the interactive lesson, both the teacher and the students are on the same level. The teacher does not teach material in these classes; instead, he or she becomes an active participant in the debate and steers it in the correct path. Any interactive class is beneficial to a person since it teaches them how to articulate themselves and defend their positions. Furthermore, in a traditional session, there is a chance of gaining new knowledge from students, but because the teacher frequently teaches the content, they are unable to impart information to the audience.

Keywords: Interactive learning, interactive activities, standard lessons, interactive lessons, discussion, exchange information, learning models, active interaction, individual contribution, mutual support, think critically, solve problems.

1. Introduction.

Interactive learning technologies are a type of learning organization in which it is difficult for a student not to participate in a collaborative, mutually supportive learning process based on the interaction of all participants in the transmission of knowledge.

Students learn to formulate their thoughts, respond quickly, and respond to replicas of the interlocutor using interactive methods of teaching English. They gain practical communication skills in the language they are studying, learn to formulate their thoughts, and respond to replicas of the interlocutor. In such classes, the teacher is no longer just a leader, but also an aide who can swiftly correct a mistake or provide the correct term. The process of learning a foreign language is substantially accelerated when using interactive techniques of teaching English. Interactive - inter (mutual), act (act). The learning process is carried out in conditions of constant, active interaction of all students. The student and teacher are equal subjects of instruction.

2. Main Part.

The educational process consists mostly of two procedures. They are both imparting and gaining knowledge. In the first case, the teacher provides knowledge to students, who then receive it. Innovative approaches also deal with this process, with the goal of evaluating a teacher's and learners' efforts utilizing new techniques and methods of teaching, including new technical means of teaching. As we already know, there are three basic types of methodological approaches to teaching foreign languages. There are three types of methods: passive, active, and interactive. If we start with passive methods, it is important to keep in mind that in passive methods, the teacher is at the center of the learning process. He takes an active role, but the students are more passive. Questions, individual and control work, tests, and other methods of control can be used. When administered by an experienced teacher, it may be beneficial. Second, learners are also active in Active methods. In the interaction process, their roles and activities are equal. Learners get the opportunity to ask

questions and share their thoughts with the teacher. The last, but now most important, interactive method or approach is an updated version of active methods. During the lesson, the majority of teachers usually comprehend or mean cooperative action. However, attention should be paid to inner action as well. Learners should be motivated from inside, resulting in active work or active engagement in class. The teacher's responsibility in the interactive method is to guide students' activities toward the lesson's goal, which includes interactive exercises and tasks.

As below some Interactive methods are included:

1. Think, pair and share

Set a problem or a question around a certain topic, and pair up your students. Give each pair of students enough time so they can reach a proper conclusion, and permit the kids to share their conclusion in their voice. This way your students will be engaged, communicating, and remember more of the class than ever before.

2. Brainstorming

Interactive brainstorming is mostly performed in group sessions. The process is useful for generating creative thoughts and ideas. Brainstorming helps students learn to work together, and above all, learn from each other. You'll be surprised by all the great ideas they come up with! Check out these 8 fun brainstorming apps you can use in your classroom, or use BookWidgets' Mindmap widget to structure thinking.

3. Buzz session

Participants come together in session groups that focus on a single topic. Within each group, every student contributes thoughts and ideas. Encourage discussion and collaboration among the students within each group. Everyone should learn from each other's input and experiences. As a teacher, you could give your students some keywords to spark the conversation.

4. Exit slips

These are best used at the end of the class session. You'll ask the students to write for one minute on a specific question. It might be generalized to "what was the most important thing you learned today". Then, you can decide if you are going to open

up a conversation about it in your next class. You can ask them if they still remember what they wrote down. Need a digital exit slip template? Try this one from BookWidgets and learn more about the possibilities of an exit slip.

5. Misconception check

Discover students' misconceptions. See if students can identify what is the correct answer when given a false fact. It's useful when going over a previous lesson. It encourages students to think deeply and wager all the possibilities.

6. Board rotation

This interactive learning strategy is even more interactive than others! Divide your class into different groups of students and assign them to each of the boards you've set up in the room. Assign one topic/question per board. After each group writes an answer, they rotate to the next board. Here, they write their answer below the first answer of the previous group. Let them go around the room until all the groups have covered all the boards. Not that many boards in your classroom? Try using tablets and BookWidgets' interactive whiteboard.

7. Pick the Winner

Divide the class into groups and let them work on the same topic/problem. Let them record an answer/strategy on paper or digitally. Then, ask the groups to switch with a nearby group and let them evaluate their answer. After a few minutes, allow each set of groups to merge and ask them to select the best answer from the two choices, which will be presented to the complete class.

3. Conclusion.

To summarize, all interactive approaches and strategies assist students improve conversational skills, help students form emotional connections, train them to work in a team, listen to their peers' opinions, and establish more close contact between students and the teacher. The utilization of interactive methods and approaches in a foreign language class decreases anxious tension among students, allows for a change in activity forms, and allows students to focus on the essential aspects of the employment theme. Finally, as the quality of the material supply and the

effectiveness of its absorption improves, so does the motivation of learners to learn a foreign language.

References:

1. Polat E.S. *Novie pedagogicheskie i informatsionnie texnologii v sisteme obrazovanie: posobie dlya studentov.* -Rostov, 2005.
Dudley-Evans T. *Developments in English for Specific Purposes.* - Cambridge University Press, 1998. -P.48.
Polat E.S. *Education in cooperation // Foreign languages at school.* - 2000. - №. 1.
2. Polat E.S. *The method of projects in the lessons of a foreign language.* - 2000. - №. 2. - P. 73.
3. Rogers K. *Questions that I would ask myself if I were a teacher \ \ anthology in pedagogical psychology comp.*
1995,
4. Useinova N.V. *Techniques for involving students in interactive activities in English classes.* - 2005. № 6. - P. 49-54.
5. Richards G. C. and Rodgers Th. S. *Approaches and Methods in Language teaching.*
USA, 1993. -P.76.